

Research Article

Effect of Fine Aggregate Sources on Compressive Strength of Cement Concrete

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A B S T R A C T

The cause of failure of structure made from cement concrete is due to use of low-quality ingredient which is used directly without testing its properties and without studying its suitability in production of different grade of concrete mix. The aim of this study is to presents that the effect of fine aggregates from different sources on compressive strength of cement concrete. For this study four fine aggregate sources were taken. Altogether 48 concrete cubes of M20 grade were prepared from different sixteen combinations of these four fine aggregate sources. The different properties were founded by conducting different laboratory tests for fine aggregates from different sources and the compressive strength test of 48 cubes was conducted.

The test results showed that properties of fine aggregate sources such as fineness modulus, loose bulk density, specific gravity, water absorption and Materials Finer than 75 μm were founded in the range of (3.17-3.88), (1508.33-1604.17) kg/m^3 , (2.57-2.66) %, (1.60-1.92) % and (2.74-7.47) respectively. Compressive strength test of all 48 samples were cross the minimum strength provided by M20 grade and it is ranges from 20.64 N/mm^2 to 32.47 N/mm^2 . Different value of mean compressive strength was obtained for all sixteen combinations of aggregates form each other. The fine aggregate from Chisang source achieved more value of average compressive strength when mix with other four different coarse aggregate sample than other three sources. Significance difference in mean compressive strength of concrete made from different fine aggregates source was concluded by the Two-way ANOVA test results. This research work concluded that all four fine aggregate sources used in this study and concrete made from these sources can be used for residential building construction propose and other construction work which required strength provided by M20 grade of nominal mix concrete.

Keywords: Cement Concrete, Fine Aggregates Sources, Properties Fine Aggregates, Compressive Strength

Introduction

In concrete, cement, water and aggregates (fine and coarse) are the basic constituents and admixtures, pigments, fibres, polymers are other constituents used in concrete can change or modify the properties of concrete (Neville and Brooks, 2010). Now a day, concrete is worldwide mostly used construction material in construction industries. In Nepal, the construction industry is the large business field and large amount of capital is invested in this field. If concrete failure occurs, there may be huge loss of investment in the industry and overall, in the economy of nation like Nepal.

Compressive strength is the significant properties of concrete which is depends on the properties and qualities of ingredient used to produce concrete. Generally, about 60-75% by volume of concrete (70-85% by mass) is occupy by the fine and coarse aggregates (Kosmatka & Wilson, 2011). In case of Nepal, various sources of aggregates are used in concrete production and the main sources of aggregates in Nepal are stream and rivers. The properties of fine aggregates from stream to stream and river to river are different. So that it is very essential to identify the effects of fine aggregates source in compressive strength of concrete.

Statement of Problem

The overall stability of concrete structure depends upon the compressive strength of concrete. The compressive strength of concrete is mainly depending upon the ingredient used to produce the concrete. One of the major ingredients which affect the concrete strength is fine aggregates. In concrete production, the use of poor-quality fine aggregate may reduce and cannot achieve the desired strength of concrete.

According to Mishra and Sharestha (2019), quality is not only the factor for selecting cement brand however one single factor is quality that determine utility of the product. In this regard, it's very important to know source impact on quality.

In Nepal, various types of structures are constructing and going to be constructed for the infrastructure development of various sector and various portion of the country. Nepal has altogether 6,000 rivers (including rivulets and tributaries) (State of Water : Nepal, nd). They all have fine aggregates of various properties. It is seen that the study of fine aggregate properties and their effect on concrete is very essential from technical and economical aspect in emerging cities like Urlabari municipality.

Objective

The general objective of this study is to analyse the effects of fine aggregates from different sources on the compressive strength of cement concrete used in research area.

Literature Review

Properties of Fine Aggregate

The aggregates passing through the 4.75mm sieve and retained in 150µm size sieve are fine aggregates (Mehta, 1999). Fine aggregates have different physical, chemical, mechanical and thermal properties (Zega et al., 2010). In the study done by (Ajagbe & Tijani, 2018) determines the different properties of different natural fine aggregates sources are tabulated as.

universal compressive strength test machine. Some of the factors that vary the compression strength i.e., aggregate

Table 1. Properties of the Fine Aggregates Sources (Ajagbe & Tijani, 2018)

Sources	Fineness Modulus	Loose Bulk Density	Specific Gravity	Water Absorption (%)	Materials Finer Than 75 µm (%)	Clay Lump & Friable Particles (%)	Sand Equivalent (%)	Presence of Organic Impurities
SR	4.0	1530	2.68	1.8	2.0	0.16	86	Not Present
AR	2.5	1480	2.67	1.2	5.0	0.32	67	Not present
MR	3.5	1550	2.69	1.7	2.8	0.70	77	Not Present
EB	1.9	1430	2.65	1.3	10.8	0.96	59	Present

Table 2. Properties of the Fine Aggregates Sources (Ajagbe & Tijani, 2018)

Sources	Fineness Modulus	Loose Bulk Density	Specific Gravity	Water Absorption (%)
Natural River Sand	2.44	1671	2.59	1.51
Manufactured Sand	2.75	1791	2.57	2.26

quality, cement strength, water content and water/ cement ratio (Noorzaei et al. 2007).

The compressive strength of concrete depends on the water to cement ratio, degree of compaction, ratio of cement to aggregate, bond between mortar and aggregate, grading, shape, strength and size of the aggregate (Abdullahi, 2012).

Effect of Ingredient on Compressive Strength

Research work done by (Ajagbe & Tijani, 2018) found in their study is that among twelve samples only five mixtures had above the minimum cube compressive strength of 25N/ mm² and they recommended these samples for the construction of the reinforced load-bearing building structural members. Other three mixtures had above the compressive strength of 20N/ mm² and recommended for the use in plain concrete construction while the remaining four mixtures had their compressive strength between 19.3N/ mm² and 17.9N/ mm². Finally, they concluded that the compressive strength depends on aggregate source.

A study done by (Nayaju & Tamrakar, 2019) to evaluate the fine aggregates from Budhi Gandaki-Narayani River which is rich in carrying natural fine aggregates from Higher and Lesser Himalayas region, the fine aggregates gradation curve showed that aggregates were varied from uniform to well graded, the deleterious materials excluding organic matter range from 0.3%-1.5% and presence of organic matter range from 0.57%-1.11%. They wrote the trend showed that the presence of inorganic deleterious material and presence of organic matter is increasing towards southern segments of the river. Study showed that the bulk density of aggregate is below 2gm/ cc, specific gravity ranges between 1.49 to 1.79, fineness modulus range from 1.36 to 3.50 and the value of water absorption ranges between 0.48 to 2.87%.

Research Gap

Nepal is a developing country which invest negligible source on research and only few research works are done from academic sector because of compulsion of research work to complete the degree in some academic field. Besides academicians, others researcher also contributes to find something new in Nepal but it is mainly focus on major cities and in the mega projects only but researcher cannot able to reach every place and at every sector of Nepal. So, to fulfil the gap in research in developed major cities with emerging cities this study is done to find the effect of fine aggregate sources in compressive strength of concrete majorly used in Uurlabari Municipality which is one of the emerging cities of Eastern Nepal.

Methodology

Study Area

The study area of this research works is the major four fine aggregate source used to produce concrete in Uurlabari

Municipality. This is an experimental study with the aim of identify the effect of fine aggregates from different sources of emerging eastern region of Nepal in compressive strength of concrete produce in that area.

Table 3. Research Matrix (Combination of Fine and Coarse Aggregates)

Sample Codes	CC	BC	MC	RC
CF	CFCC	CFBC	CFMC	CFRC
BF	BFCC	BFBC	BFMC	BFRC
MF	MFCC	MFBC	MFMC	MFRC
RF	RFCC	RFBC	RFMC	RFRC

Sampling

The fine and coarse aggregates collected from these four sources were used to make concrete cube as per following combination shown in Table 3, below. Three cubes were made from all sixteen combinations for M20 grade concrete. There were altogether 48 cubes for M20 grade of nominal mix concrete.

- CF = Chisang fine quarry
 BF = Bakrah fine quarry
 MF = Mawa fine quarry
 RF = Ratuwa fine quarry
 CC = Chisang coarse quarry
 BC = Bakrah coarse quarry
 MC = Mawa coarse quarry
 RC = Ratuwa coarse quarry

Data Collection

For this research work fine and coarse aggregates from different sources were collected from the following locations.

Table 4. Locations of Aggregates Collection From Different Sources

S. No.	Fine and Coarse Aggregates Sources	Northing	Easting	Reduced Level
1	Chishang Khola	26°42'44	87°29'27	213m
2	Bakraha Khola	26°43'13	87°37'51	146m
3	Mawa Khola	26°43'24	87°40'01	163m
4	Ratuwa Khola	26°44'09	87°42'29	182m

The following test was carried out on the labs of "Madan Bhandari Memorial Academy Nepal-MBMAN". During laboratory test of concrete properties of cement, water/ cement ratio and use of chemical and admixtures were remained unchanged throughout the study.

Test on Coarse Aggregate Properties

Fineness modulus Test

Fineness modulus of fine aggregates is an index number which represents the mean size of the particles in sand. It is obtained by performing sieve analysis. The cumulative percentage retained on each sieve is added and subtracted by 100 gives the value of fineness modulus. The following test procedure was adopted to obtain fineness modulus as per (IS 2386-1 (1963)).

Specific Gravity and Water Absorption Test

Specific gravity test of aggregates was conducted to measure the strength or quality of the material.

Water absorption test was conducted to determine the water holding capacity of coarse and fine aggregates. The following procedure were conducted to determine the specific gravity and water absorption of fine and coarse aggregates as per (IS 2386-3 (1963)).

Loose Bulk Density Test

Loose bulk density is the ratio of loose mass per unit volume of aggregate samples which was calculated by using the procedure mention below as per (IS 2386-3 (1963) Methods of Test for Aggregates f. Pdf, n.d.).

Material Finer Than 75µm

The test of material finer than 75µm of fine aggregates sample was calculated by following the procedure listed below as per (IS 2386-1 (1963): Methods of Test for Aggregates for Concrete, Part I: Particle Size and Shape, 1963).

Compressive Strength Test

The compressive strength of concrete was done as per guideline given by (IS 516 (1959): Method of Tests for Strength of Concrete, 1959). Three specimens of same aggregate combination were prepared as per IS 516 (1959) and was tested on universal compression testing machine after 28 days of curing and crushing strength of the specimen was recorded.

Compressive Strength of Concrete cube =

$$\frac{\text{Peak load at which it break (N)}}{\text{Corss – sectional area of that cube(mm}^2\text{)}}$$

Mean Compressive strength =

$$\frac{\text{Sum of compressive strength of three sample}}{3}$$

Analysis of Data

Compressive Strength of Cement Concrete

Compressive strength test of the various sample combination

of aggregates from different sources, the mean obtained value of compressive strength of each combination was compared with standard compressive strength of concrete mix (M20 grade). The comparison between tested value and standard value analysed the effect of aggregate sources on compressive strength of concrete.

Table 5. Setting up Two-way ANOVA table

Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	Degrees of Freedom	Mean sum of Square	F-ratio
Between rows	SSR	(r-1)	$MSR = \frac{SSR}{r-1}$	$F_r = \frac{MSR}{MSE}$
Between columns	SSC	(c-1)	$MRS = \frac{SSC}{c-1}$	$F_r = \frac{MSR}{MSE}$
Errors	SSE	(r-1)(c-1)	$MSE = \frac{SSE}{(r-1)(c-1)}$	
Total	SST	rc-1		

For the test of significance of test results two-way ANOVA test was carried out based on hypothesis testing. The dependent variable was the compressive strength with respect to independent variable (fine and coarse aggregates). Two-way ANOVA table was set of as Table 5.

SSR = Sum of Square of Rows

SSC = Sum of Square of Columns

SSE = Squares due to Error

SST = Total of Sum of Squares

r = No. of Rows

c = No. of Columns

Result and Discussion

Properties of Fine Aggregates

The following properties of fine aggregates were obtained after conducting the laboratory test. Table 6, shows the summary results of different properties of fine aggregate taken from four sources for this study. These properties were obtained by the procedure comply with IS standard series of test on properties of aggregates which is already mention in the methodology chapter.

From sieve analysis test it was obtained that the percentage of gravels and sand of fine aggregates of different sources were different and percentage of fines were same i.e., 0.5% which is shown in Table 7.

The particle size distribution curve of Chisang fine aggregates is shown in the graph below. From the calculation of sieve analysis data of Chisang fine aggregates, the particle size corresponding to 60%, 30% and 10% finer i.e., the value of D60, D30 and D10 were found as 2.1433, 0.9278 and 0.46 respectively. The value of Uniformity Coefficient (Cu)

greater than 6 for sand is considered as well graded sand and less than 4 is considered as poorly graded sand and the value of Coefficient of Curvature (Cc) for well graded sand is ranges from 1 to 3 (Terzaghi, 1959). From the calculation of CF, value of Uniformity Coefficient (Cu) and Coefficient of Curvature (Cc) of CF source were calculated as 4.659 and 0.8731 respectively. It is seen that the Cu of CF is less

than 6 and more than 4 and the value of Cc is less than 1 i.e., the fine aggregates from Chisang fine is moderately graded. Correspondingly, the value of Uniformity Coefficient (Cu) and Coefficient of Curvature (Cc) of BF source were calculated as 3.32 and 0.6767 respectively. From the value of Cu and Cc of BF source it can say that the fine aggregates for this source is poorly graded.

Figure 6. Particle Size Distribution Curve of Chishang Fine (CF)

S. No.	Sample Codes	Fineness Modulus	Loose Bulk Density (Kg/ m ³)	Specific Gravity	Water Absorption (%)	Materials Finer than 75 μ m (%)
1	CF	3.88	1547.5	2.66	1.79	2.74
2	BF	3.195	1514.167	2.63	1.68	3.69
3	MF	3.70	1604.17	2.65	1.92	2.55
4	RF	3.17	1508.33	2.57	1.60	7.47

Table 7. Proportion of Gravel, Sand and Fines in fine Aggregates of Different Sources

S.No.	Source	% Gravel	% Sand	% Fines	Total %
1	Chisang Khola	12.5	87	0.5	100
2	Bakraha Khola	10.5	89	0.5	100
3	Mawa Khola	10	89.5	0.5	100
4	Ratuwa Khola	9.5	90	0.5	100

Figure 1. Particle size Distribution Curve of Chishang Fine (CF)

Figure 2. Particle Size Distribution Curve of Bakraha Fine (BF)

Further more, calculations gave the Uniformity Coefficient (Cu) and Coefficient of Curvature (Cc) of MF source were 5.92 and 0.831 respectively. As the value of Cu is greater than 4 and nearly equal to 6, the fine aggregates from MF source are moderately graded. Similarly, the Uniformity Coefficient (Cu) and Coefficient of Curvature (Cc) of RF source was calculated as 4.2278 and 0.9001. RF has also the value of Cu is greater than 4 and Cc is nearly equal to 1 it can also be said that it is moderately graded. From this study, it is seen that if some refining process is done then from all four source the well graded fine aggregates is obtained.

The Fineness Modulus (FM) of fine aggregates of four fine sources CF, BF, MF and RF were taken in this study were obtained as 3.88, 3.195, 3.695 and 3.17 respectively. The value of fineness modulus specify the proportions of coarse and fine aggregates i.e, more the value of FM coarser the aggregates and less value of FM indicates finer the aggregates (Dhir et al., 2017). Form the obtained value of FM of four sources the fine aggregates from CF and MF are coarser than that of BF and RF.

Some of the research done in properties of aggregate by different researcher mention in section 2.1.2 of literature review of this study, the value of fineness modulus obtained in this study is as much similar and within the range of the other researcher.

The calculated value of loose bulk density of CF, BF, MF and RF were 1547.5 Kg/ m³, 1514.167 Kg/ m³, 1604.17 Kg/ m³ and 1508.33 Kg/ m³ respectively. From these values it is observed that MF source has higher value of loose bulk density than other sources and the RF source has lowest one among four. (Ajagbe & Tijani, 2018) found the values of loose bulk density of different fine aggregates sources as 1530 Kg/ m³, 1480 Kg/ m³, 1550 Kg/ m³ and 1430 Kg/ m³. Likewise, (Reddy et al., 2015) calculated LBD as 1671 Kg/ m³ and 1791 Kg/ m³ for natural and manufactured sand in his study. Accordingly, the calculated values of LBD of this study as much as similar to the other research works.

Form specific gravity test it is observed that the value of SG is different for sample taken from different sources. The CF source has the highest value 2.66 of SG among four sources and RF source has lowest value 2.57 of SG. Other sources BF and MF have 2.63 and 2.65 value of SG respectively. (A.K, 2019) wrote normal sand have SG from 2.65 to 2.67 but SG ranges from 2.5 to 3 can be used in road construction work. In the study done by (Ajagbe & Tijani, 2018), they found the SG of four fine sources in the range between 2.65 to 2.69. This research found SG of fine sources ranges from 2.57 to 2.66 which is acceptable.

Form the observation and calculation the water absorption test of CF, BF, MF and RF was found as 1.79%, 1.68%, 1.92%

and 1.60% respectively. It can be said that the aggregates from MF source absorb more water than other sources and RF source has low capacity to absorb water. (Yacoub et al., 2017)2017 found WA for natural sand was 2.3% and for recycled sand 6.86%. Similarly, (Reddy et al., 2015) calculated the value of WA for natural and manufactured sand was 1.51% and 2.26% respectively. (Neville & Brooks, 2010) wrote the value of WA should not greater than 2% if exceed soundness test is required.

Test showed RF source contain more materials finer than 75µm in fine aggregates than other sources. The test results for materials finer than 75µm were obtained for CF, BF, MF and RF are 2.74%, 3.69%, 2.55% and 7.47% respectively. Limits for fine aggregates for uncrushed is 3%, for crushed is 15% and for manufacture is 10% (Gambhir, 2004). (Ajagbe & Tijani, 2018) obtained the value of materials finer than 75µm from test for four different naturals sources were in range from 2 to 10.8%.

Effect on Compressive Strength of Concrete

The mean compressive strength of different sixteen sample mix were obtained by laboratory test are tabulated as below in Table 8 The concrete cube made up of M20 grade of nominal mix concrete give the minimum value of compressive strength of 20 N/ mm² after 28 days curing testing on compression test machine(Tantawi, 2015). In the table 8, the 28 days compressive strength of all combinations ranges from 20.64 N/ mm² to 32.47 N/ mm². This study shows the concrete made from all the combinations of coarse aggregate sources meet the minimum value of compressive strength which should be given by M20 grade of concrete similar to Aryal and Mishra (2020).

In respect of concrete made from fine aggregate sources with different coarse aggregate samples used in this study, it was seen that the CF source gave the highest value of average of compressive strength of 27.69 N/ mm² and RF gave the lowest value of 23.62 N/ mm² while BF and MF gave the value 24.75 N/ mm² and 26.12 N/ mm² respectively.

The compressive strength of cement concrete depend upon the various factors at which production of concrete is made. They may be water cement ratios, properties of cement, properties of aggregates, other admixtures used in concrete (Abdullahi, 2012). (Ajagbe & Tijani, 2018) determined the 28 days compressive strength of concrete cube of M15 grade made up of different combinations of four fine and three coarse aggregates from different sources in the range from 17.9 N/ mm² to 29.43 N/ mm². Also in this study, the mean compressive strength of different sixteen combinations of different fine aggregates form different sources with different coarse aggregate sample are different. The significant difference in mean compressive

strength of fine aggregate sources analysed through two-way ANOVA test.

Two-way ANOVA Analysis of Mean Compressive Strength

The results of test statistic of two-way ANOVA test are presented in the Table 9 below. The 5% significance level is taken to obtain the value of F from the statistical table.

From statistical table, tabulated value of F-ratio for between

rows i.e., $F(3,9)$ at 0.05 level of significance is equal to 3.8625. As the calculated F-ratio 8.7832 is greater than that of tabulated F-ratio 3.8625, the null hypothesis, H_0 which is already set on analysis of data section of methodology chapter for fine aggregate source is rejected and the alternative hypothesis, H_1 is accepted. Hence there is significant difference between rows. That means there is significant difference in all the means of compressive strength of concrete produced by fine aggregate sources.

Table 8. Mean Value of Compressive Strength of Sixteen Combinations

Sample Codes	CC	BC	MC	RC	Average	W/C Ratio (Constant)	Mix Proportion (Constant)	Cement Brand/grade (Constant)	Total no. of Cubes
CF	32.47	26.83	27.58	23.87	27.69	0.5	1:1.5:3 Nominal Mix of M20 Grade	Shivam 43 Grade	12
BF	27.88	24.25	25.57	21.29	24.75				12
MF	28.54	26.78	26.30	22.86	26.12				12
RF	28.34	20.64	24.34	21.16	23.62				12
Average	29.31	24.63	25.95	22.30	-	Total			48

Figure 3. Particle Size Distribution Curve of Bakraha fine (BF)

Table 9. Two-way ANOVA Table of Test Statistic

Source of Variation	Sums of Squares SS	Degrees of Freedom DF	Mean Squares MS	F-ratio (Calculated)
Between rows (Fine Source)	37.0502	3	12.3501	8.7832
Between columns (Coarse Source)	102.9092	3	34.3031	24.3959
Error (residual)	12.6549	9	1.4061	
Total	152.6144	15		

Conclusion and Recommendation

Conclusion

- All four fine aggregates sources meet their properties to use for the residential building construction purpose
- All fine aggregate samples from different sources achieved the value of mean compressive strength when used to produce concrete so, that all sources can be used for normal concrete works of construction
- Fine aggregates from Chisang source can be used in construction projects where less safety factor is considered and risk factor is high
- The fine aggregates sources affect the strength of concrete made from them i.e., compressive strength of concrete vary from fine aggregates sources

Recommendation

- The concrete produce from all fine aggregate sources achieves the minimum strength should provide by the M20 grade of concrete can recommended for use of the production normal concrete and for residential building construction purpose
- Some source possesses good properties and gives high compressive strength can recommended to use for high strength concrete works

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